

Title: “Money is only a tool. It will take you wherever you wish, but it will not replace you as the driver.” - Ayn Rand

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INTRODUCTION:

With all of these cryptocurrency and digital assets on the market, how to differentiate good projects from bad projects.

AIM:

To help the audience understand my personal investment philosophy and decisions. Using this to shed some light on their future investment decisions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Going through a few examples of how to research about cryptocurrency and where to get information about them. How to keep track of their progress of these projects/investments.

RESULTS:

Since 2015, we have returned 368% on our bitcoin holdings, and more than 2000% in fiat equivalent.

CONCLUSIONS:

It's not difficult to make money in an upmarket, the real way to measure returns is in bitcoins or ether rather than fiat. The more you investigate, the less you have to invest.

KEYWORDS:

Bitcoin, ICO, Ethereum, Blockchain.

BIOGRAPHY:

Rui Dong has completed his Double major from Western University of Canada and worked as an Actuary for 3 years after graduation. He is a fund manager of a private fund. He looks for "dividend" generating opportunities within the cryptocurrency space. Second to that is to write about the industry from the perspective of an investor. Since end of 2015, the have returned over 368.6% on bitcoin holdings. Counting from April 2013, the fund has returned more than X25 for their initial investors.

(Up to 100 words)